

An Automatic Misleading Graph Detection Tool

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Extended Abstract

Graphs help people to understand facts and claims in documents [1], but some graphs in these documents are manipulated to reach specific goals of some authors, such as exaggerating effects in their claims [2, 3, 4]. These manipulations in financial reports might change some readers' understandings of the documents [5], and consequently, these readers might waste their time and other resources to follow-up on these financial reports as investment decisions. Similarly, in scientific research, some readers might decide to reproduce the result of a scientific article because the misleading graphs in this article mislead these readers.

Figure 1: two modified examples of misleading graph in PubMed Open Access Data Set

Given this potential concern for science, we conducted an exploratory study on how common misleading graphs are used among scientific articles in PubMed Open Access Data Set. In this study, we classified a graph to a misleading graph if it has multiple y axes, or the scale changes midstream or the y axis of a bar chart doesn't start at zero [6]. We examined six subsets in PubMed Open Access Data Set, and we found two misleading graphs (see Figure 1) among 360 bar charts in these subsets. It would be necessary for researchers, the public and the government to know if the popularity of misleading graph in this exploratory study can be generalized to a bigger scope of scientific articles because if so, publication policy might need to be modified to reduce the number of misleading graphs in scientific articles.

However this examination process is very tedious and time consuming, therefore we develop an automatic misleading graph detection tool for graphs with misleading axes. This tool has four steps of analysis for the detection of misleading graphs. First, we detect bar charts and

line charts from graphs with an object-recognition model [7]. To train this model, we labeled panels in a number of multi-panel graphs in PubMed Open Access Data Set. Second, we detect texts in the graphs with the same object-recognition model [7]. In this step, we apply training data from interactive data lab to train our object-recognition model, and this training data consists of millions of academic graphs with labeled text [8]. Third, identify roles of texts with an open source classification model, trained with academic graphs with labeled roles [9]. In this step, this classification model helps us to identify texts in y axis and x axis, so that we can further detect misleading axes. Fourth, recognize graphs with misleading axes with a rule-based method [10, 6]. More specifically, given the texts on the axes, we can examine if the y axis of a bar chart starts with zero, if this chart has two y axes or if this chart changes the scale in the axes midstream. Following these four steps, we can detect misleading graphs in academic graphs. This method will be applied to the full PubMed Open Access Data Set to detect graphs with misleading axes in biomedical scientific articles. This tool can help us to investigate the seriousness of the abuse use of misleading graphs in biomedical scientific articles. In addition, this technique can help readers to recognize misleading graphs efficiently, and journal editors might apply this technique to submitted manuscripts.

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